

Jean Monnet Module

‘DEBATING EUROPE’

INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL DYNAMICS OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION

(DEBUE)

Best Student Scenario-Building Papers for Europe 2030

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INTRODUCTION

This report presents papers from scenario-building exercises carried out in the context of the Jean Monnet DEBUE module. Beginning with a brief overview of scenario-building methodologies deployed,¹ some of the most insightful student papers based on the ‘best’, ‘worst’ and ‘wildcard’ future scenarios for the European Union (EU) in 2030 are presented.

DEBUE’s Scenario-building Methodologies

Scenario building exercises are critical tools for navigating complexity and uncertainty. In the context of the Jean Monnet EU-funded DEBUE module these exercises got students to actively confront multiple, dramatically different futures for Europe and the world, from cooperation to fragmentation and beyond. As a learning and teaching methodology, scenario-building cultivates strategic foresight, systems thinking, intercultural understanding, as well as policy understanding. Scenario-building also responds to the pedagogical priorities and transversal skills emphasised in EU higher-education policy.

Turning Point / Normative Approach to Scenario-building – EU in 2030

First, a short scenario brief is developed and shared with students to emphasise the ‘turning point’. This prompts students to start their forward-looking analysis.

Sample Scenario Brief

‘Europe 2030: The End of Assumptions’

Since the 1950s, European integration has survived by confronting crises and seizing the opportunity for reinvention. From the Cold War’s end to the eurozone crisis, migration challenges, and the pandemic, every turning point has tested but arguably bolstered the EU’s capacity to adapt and move forward. What began as a post-war economic project, the EU has become a Union of twenty-seven states.

However, as Europe sprints towards 2030 and beyond, its familiar compass points have gone adrift. By launching its war on Ukraine Russia is aiming to redraw the continent’s contours. Meanwhile, NATO’s unity seems to be wavering as US politics takes multiple unpredictable turns. The persistence of ‘Trumpism’ in American foreign and security policy raises profound doubts about Europe’s ability to rely on the United States for its leadership.

Beyond Europe, a deeper reordering of power is underway. China has become not only an economic powerhouse but also a political magnet for the Global South. Through the BRICS, the Belt and Road Initiative, and its networks of influence in Africa, Asia and Central Asia, Beijing offers an alternative vision of governance and development, which is appealing to

¹ The detailed DEBUE curriculum guide can be found as open access here: - <https://zenodo.org/records/17532744>

many. The BRICS+ grouping now accounts for a growing share of global GDP and trade, and also controls raw materials essential for the green transition. The West's legitimacy is essentially contested.

Climate change intensifies the fault lines in international relations and is a threat multiplier and a defining driver of Europe's politics, security and economy. Europe's environmental ambitions have become geopolitical, shaping relations with Africa and Asia as the continent seeks to secure access to lithium, cobalt, hydrogen, and critical raw materials.

Inside the Union, cohesion seems to be unstable. In several member and candidate states, oligarchic networks, disinformation machines and illiberal leaders are eroding accountability and dividing their societies via polarisation. Democracy, the rule of law, and equality, which were previously core governance principles are being contested, as seen in multiple instances of democratic backsliding. Misogyny, anti-gender politics, and cultural polarisation have also re-entered the mainstream. The EU's authority to enforce its own rules is questioned from within.

Above all of this lies the key question: - should the EU enlarge or stay as it is?

Will bringing Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia, and the Western Balkans into the EU make Europe stronger and a more coherent geopolitical force, or weaker due to instabilities, corruption, and new lines of division seeping into the Union? Enlargement is a 'European gamble', it seems. For some, it is a moral and strategic imperative and a chance to secure democracy in East / South East Europe and to prove that the EU remains a transformative and meaningful power. For others, it is a dangerous illusion, since expansion without consolidation and deep reform could paralyse the EU and entrench dividing lines. Chances are that by 2030, the question of enlargement will no longer be theoretical. If the EU expands to 33 or 35 members, what happens to its institutions, budget, and identity? Will Europe become a geopolitical actor on the world stage or will it evolve into a loose confederation?

Europe's global relevance will depend on how it responds to such dilemmas. Will it remain a normative power setting global economic standards and pursuing the rule of law, or become a regional actor in a world potentially dominated by China, the BRICS, and climate chaos? What kind of Europe will exist in 2030? Your task is not to predict the future but to construct it by exploring the choices, shocks, and turning points that will determine what kind of Europe we will live in in 2030.

Step-by-step guide

Step	Activity
1	<p>Divide into three teams of four to six students. Each team should represent a different paradigm:</p> <p>Team one - Best-case – What would a highly positive European outcome look like? Which choices make it possible? What needs to occur for this to come about?</p> <p>Team two - Worst-case – What might failure or regression mean? What would need to happen / not happen for this to come about?</p> <p>Team three - Wild-card – What unexpected disruption could change everything – a technological breakthrough, geopolitical shock, social movement, environmental incident?</p>
2	<p>Students research and identify 'drivers'. They should begin the research process by identifying major drivers of change that influence the topic. These will be political, social, demographic, technological, economic, environmental, or legal.</p> <p>It is important that drivers are not seen in terms of isolated silos, but rather dynamically and interactive. Reliable and verifiable data based on primary and good-quality secondary academic and policy sources should be used. Students need to distinguish between predictable/ongoing trends and major uncertainties.</p>
3	<p>Students retreat into their paradigm groups and start to work out their main drivers and also what it means to be best, worst and wildcard.</p>
4	<p>Alongside their research, the teams write two to three pages describing its future scenario as a draft. Narratives should outline key events, actor responses, and implications and outcomes.</p>
5	<p>Teams present their scenarios in 15-20 minutes, using visuals or slides to illustrate key features. Following each presentation, questions about plausibility, logic, and evidence are put to the teams. Teams should respond constructively and note feedback for revision.</p>
6	<p>Teams refine their papers in light of their presentations and feedback and then submit their papers – aiming at 5 - 6 pages</p>
7	<p>Final class debrief and feedback, lessons learned and links to 'real' debates.</p>

Matrix Approach to Scenario-building for EU enlargement by 2030

The matrix approach to scenario building gives students focus and clarity, especially in the early stages of learning about the EU. By limiting analysis to two critical drivers it means that they engage with the most impactful variables. This results in four scenarios that are plausible, distinct and coherent.

Step-by-step guide

Step	Activity
1	Introductory lectures.
2	Design the matrix, with students as co-creators. Select two high-impact uncertainties to form the axes of a 2x2 matrix. Subsequently, the four squares create four distinct 'futures' (see below).
3	Divide into four teams of four to six students. Clarify responsibilities and roles early on so that each member contributes research, analysis, and creative input
4	Introduce the Matrix and make sure that everyone understands it. Carefully explain was the axis mean; - <i>Vertical</i> : EU Political Cohesion (High - Low). High cohesion in practice means fast, unanimous decision-making and agreement on core values. Whereas low means states are likely to use vetoes, coalitions of the willing emerge and potential policy paralysis emerges. <i>Horizontal</i> : The pace of reforms in EU candidate states (Fast - Slow).
5	Define the four squares, go over the four predetermined scenarios to explain how the combination of the two variables leads to the outcomes and resulted assumed in the matrix.
6	Assign one of the four quadrants (squares) to each group. At this stage, teams move towards 'creative synthesis' by transforming their assigned quadrant into a plausible, evidence-based narrative of the EU enlargement process. The following process is followed: - Teams start by defining a common baseline namely where is Europe positioned today along the two axes EU political cohesion and the pace of candidate reforms? What concrete developments define this current reality: the war in Ukraine, Hungary's veto politics, the green transition, enlargement fatigue, or new geopolitical alignments (amongst many others)? This baseline anchors the scenario and importantly, prevents unstructured speculation and drift away from logic. Next, students should list five to seven critical drivers shaping EU enlargement towards the year 2030. These must include political, economic, social, environmental, and technological factors. It is important to classify them into: - predetermined/strong existing trends that are likely to persist, such as digitalisation, climate urgency, demographic decline, and critical uncertainties the outcomes of which could shift the future, such as regime change in a candidate country, EU constitutional reform, an environmental catastrophe, or a major wave of migration wave. In their teams the students then discuss how these forces interact and which combinations might push/pull their scenario toward the quadrant's logic: - 'United and Expanding, Selective Integration, Fragmented Europe, or Frozen Enlargement.

7	Students build a timeline from 2025 through to 2030 by mapping five to six ‘turning points’ that connect the ‘present’ to the envisioned 2030. Each milestone should be able to answer: Who acts? (EU institutions, member states, candidate governments, other external powers); What changes? (policies, institutions, alliances, social dynamics) What comes next? (effects on cohesion, reform pace and stages, and legitimacy of EU enlargement processes). This links ‘structure to agency’.
8	Write up the narrative in a 2000-word scenario paper following this type of structure: - Short overview to describe what Europe looks like in 2030. Has enlargement advanced, stalled, or split? What is the general political and social climate in Europe? Talk about drivers and triggers to identify your 5–6 key forces that shape this future. Provide a chronology of 2025 through to 2030. In other words, tell the story of how Europe moved from today to 2030. What events / decisions caused change to occur? Use milestones. Mention 2–3 recommendations: what should EU leaders or candidate governments do to move towards best outcomes and avoid the worst?
9	Groups present their 10-minute narrative. Finally, ask the students to assume the role of European Commission President and answer the following question; <i>knowing these four potential futures, what core policy recommendation would you make today to avoid the worst-case scenarios and accelerate towards the best one?</i>

EU Enlargement Scenarios Matrix

Scenario Papers

The following student scenario papers represent creative outputs from the DEBUE Jean Monnet Module. Scenario-building is central to DEBUE's high-impact pedagogy which seeks to move learning away from the classroom towards real-world foresight when it comes to EU studies. Using the Turning Point and Matrix methods described above, students were encouraged to think strategically about how Europe might evolve by 2030, by identifying key variables, shocks, trends and policy choices that could potentially drive and shape Europe and its role in the world over the next decade.

The scenarios presented below suggest that students approach the European project with a mixture of critical optimism and realism in that they recognise the Union's fragility and limitations but also its transformative potential and power of attraction. Across the best-case, worst-case and wild-card scenarios, a coherent picture emerges of what matters most. Democracy, equality, climate security and solidarity are consistently seen as the cornerstones of Europe's future. Conversely, corruption, inequality, disinformation and gender regression appear as the main sources of decline. Interestingly, students tended to select variables that reflect current EU debates about the rule of law, energy transitions, enlargement, digital transformations, migration and global competitiveness, but tended to reframe them in terms of human impact, justice and moral choices. Equally, many scenarios integrated global dimensions which demonstrates an acute awareness of the interdependencies between Europe's destiny and the fate of its neighbours.

Best-case scenarios tend to depict a Europe that regains strategic confidence through inclusion and systemic reforms. The EU is cast as a moral and ecologically aware superpower, capable of combining growth with equality and climate responsibility. Equally, enlargement and solidarity are seen as drivers of renewal and gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights emerge as a defining measure of progress. These lines of reasoning suggest that students believe in European integration, but only if it remains democratic, open and progressive.

Worst-case scenarios reveal anxieties about democratic backsliding, social polarisation and the loss of moral and normative direction in Europe. Europe's potential failure and collapse stems less from external threats and more from internal complacency and a drift away from the rule of law, tolerance and trust. Students also make a strong link between authoritarianism and gender inequality, showing a very sharp awareness of how identity politics can be very easily weaponised against democracy.

Wild-card scenarios are the most inventive and blend geopolitics, technological challenges and environmental shocks. Some scenarios imagine radical transformations resulting from ecological collapse, new forms of digital autocracy or the rebirth of civic movements. Others blended fiction and foresight to ascertain how novel or unexpected events could reshape institutions and where and how people live. Together, these scenarios demonstrated that Europe's future is likely to depend not only on treaties but also on values, human agency and imagination.

Best Case Scenarios

United We Stand, Divided We Fall

'In varietate concordia or United in Diversity; in 2030 the EU's motto still captures its critical essence and purpose that peace and prosperity arise from cooperation among nations. Despite turbulence and external aggression from the side of Russia, the EU has endured, proving that over 70 years after its creation it is a resilient system able to adapt to new realities. The EU has maintained its coherence by focusing on unity in a world marked by volatility and polarisation.

Enlargement: from fatigue to a geopolitical imperative

Following Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine in 2022, the urgency of EU enlargement shifted forwards. What was once a cautious and technical process became a geopolitical necessity. The EU realised this already in 2023 when it invited Ukraine, Georgia and Moldova to become candidates. The invasion forced Brussels to reimagine enlargement as a tool of stability and defence. Reform-minded governments in the Western Balkans accelerated their alignment with the EU acquis, and enlargement became a symbol of strategic resilience. By 2029, several candidate states, notably North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Albania, had completed accession negotiations and were offered membership. Serbia's position remained ambiguous, caught between Brussels and Moscow, while Turkey's path continued to be obstructed by human rights divergences. In the run up to 2030 the change in tone was clear: enlargement was no longer treated as a burden but as a guarantee of Europe's collective security and survival. The Union recognised that its credibility as a geopolitical actor depended on keeping its neighbourhood firmly anchored to the European model.

After Brexit: a smaller but more cohesive Union

Still in 2030 Brexit continues to shape Europe's 'political psychology'. While the UK is still unlikely to rejoin, relations have stabilised through cooperation in trade and security. It is now evident that Brexit strengthened EU cohesion. With one of its most Eurosceptic members gone, integration in digital policy, migration, finance and home affairs advanced as never before. Populist governments in Hungary and Poland remain within the EU, constrained by financial penalties and peer pressure for breaches of the rule of law, but since their citizens remain very pro-EU the likelihood for them leaving the EU is very low. The lesson of Brexit is clear: leaving the Union is possible, but economically punishing and politically isolating.

Economy, trade and transatlantic relations

By 2030, the EU economy remained one of the world's most powerful, characterised by adaptability and strong institutions. Free-trade agreements with India, Indonesia, and regions fora such as Mercosur have diversified markets, while the euro retained its global standing and even improved due to problems with the US dollar. Competition from digital currencies has intensified, yet the euro's stability and reputation as a rules-based currency underpinned its influence.

By 2030 in a post-Trump era, relations with the United States were on the mend. Washington's strategic focus shifting toward Asia, means that Europe has had to take more responsibility for its own defence, which is boosted by its enlargement policies. While a fully fledged EU Army is unlikely, a European Security Council is in place, signalling a more autonomous European defence culture.

Migration, demography and solidarity

In 2030 migration remained one of Europe's biggest challenges. The EU's new solidarity mechanism, combining relocation, financial support, and return sponsorship, finally progressed in the late 2020's and after years of wrangling in Brussels, it has helped distribute migrants more fairly among member states. While divisions persist, the demographic reality of an ageing Europe has reframed migration as a necessity for economic survival rather than a political or cultural threat. By 2030 the discourse about immigrants in Europe has changed and is progressive. By 2030, progress toward a common migration and asylum framework was regarded as a key indicator of Europe's maturity and resilience.

Conclusion: resilience as Europe's defining trait

By 2030, the EU became an influential, adaptive, and resilient actor. It has weathered wars, pandemics, and populism. Enlargement, once dismissed, has been revived by necessity. Brexit has tested but not broken the Union, and ultimately, the EU in 2030 has shown that unity, remains its most valuable strategic asset.

Ascent of the Brussels Consensus

By 2030, the EU stands at the centre of a world it helped to repair. The turbulent 2020s, which were marked by pandemics, wars, and climate shocks gave way to a renaissance of democracy, cooperation, and moral authority. Europe's characteristic blend of law, values, and vision has become the benchmark for global governance. This new age is called the 'Brussels Consensus', which sees that rules, justice, and sustainability outweigh hard power.

Post-Trump, China's retreat and the Brussels Consensus

The turning point came in 2026. Former President Donald Trump's conviction for financial misconduct ended a decade of paralysis. Two years later, President Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez entered office. Her Green New Deal diplomacy and internationalist outlook refreshed the transatlantic alliance. Washington funded global climate initiatives and supported a permanent EU role in the G20 Security Forum. The relationship was about shared purpose. Meanwhile, China faltered. A demographic crunch, energy shortages, and resistance from the Global South to debt-based BRI projects forced Beijing to retreat. The BRICS bloc fragmented as Brazil, India, and South Africa deepened cooperation with Europe's green investment agenda. By 2030 the Brussels Consensus supplanted the old Washington model, promoting sustainable development, inclusive growth and transparent governance. Power no longer flowed from dominance but from credibility—and Europe's moral authority became the world's most valuable currency.

Within Europe, the war in Ukraine ended in 2027 through a settlement co-brokered by the EU and African Union. Reconstruction became the Union's test-bed. The European Renewal Fund tied aid to democratic reform, transforming Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia into

showcases of Europe's power and purpose. By 2030, the Union counted thirty-three members, its institutions reformed for both scale and cohesion. New voices from the East and South injected realism into debates on security, migration and climate.

Climate Leadership, Culture and Normative Power

The Green Deal 2.0 of 2028, fused technology, equality and sustainability. Europe became the first continent to achieve net-zero emissions, low unemployment and affordable energy. Massive investment in hydrogen corridors and the circular economy renewed regions across the EU. By 2030, across the world the Brussels Consensus was seen as proof that growth, justice, and climate responsibility could co-exist.

The EU also rediscovered its ideals. The European Civic Charter enshrined gender equality, digital rights, and academic freedom as pillars of EU citizenship. Illiberal movements waned as voters demanded fairness above wealth. Civic education and media literacy became central to schooling, which helped turn populism into an anachronism. The Brussels Consensus extended beyond economics by becoming a moral contract linking prosperity to integrity and progress. Brussels evolved into the world's arbitration and mediation hub. From AI to ocean governance, global actors sought European help and validation. Africa's Free Trade Area linked with the single market. The Global Gateway initiative overtook BRI in scale and reputation, built on transparency, local ownership and environmental / climate safeguards.

By 2030 Europe was showing what responsible power looks like. Where others projected dominance, Europe projected consent; where others promoted ideology, the EU exported standards and norms. The Brussels Consensus crystallised this transformation.

Across the Atlantic, the United States complemented the EU's role. In late 2029 the Transatlantic Climate-Security Alliance was jointly launched by President Ocasio-Cortez and European leaders, merging NATO's deterrence with green transition financing for vulnerable states. China, pragmatic after a decade of strain, joined Europe and the US in early 2030 in establishing frameworks for AI and data protection.

At home, Europeans felt renewal in daily life. Energy was clean and local, cities greener and elections calmer. Migration was managed through cooperative partnerships and investment in health and education strengthened public trust across the EU. Already before 2030, young Europeans saw public service as a calling. The EU's approval ratings reached record highs.

Reforging the West: Europe Takes the Helm

A turning point occurred in late 2025 when after years of economic stagnation, fragmented politics, and diplomatic isolation the UK government embarked on a path to re-join the EU. A new generation of leaders, many from the ruling Green Party campaigned to rejoin and rebuild Europe. Negotiations were quick and a consensus was reached; Britain's re-entry in 2027 provided an impulse for EU renewal. The deal gave London leading roles in digital regulation, climate finance, and defence innovation which reflected the UK's profile and reputation. A London-Berlin-Paris-Warsaw quad became Europe's new strategic engine, which helped break decades of inertia and flaccidity; consequently, for the first time in almost a generation, Europe was looking outward with ambition.

Energy independence and expansion

Europe's resurgence was powered by the achievement of energy self-sufficiency. Between 2022 and 2027, the EU quietly built the foundations of a post-fossil world; offshore wind complexes in the North Sea, solar corridors across Southern Europe, and hydrogen highways that linked Portugal to Poland and beyond were constructed. By the time Russia collapsed into civil war in 2027, Europe no longer depended on imported gas or oil. This was an emancipatory turning point for the EU. The EU also turned eastwards. Ukraine's reconstruction, which was based on the EU's Acquis, became a template for democratic transformations elsewhere with Moldova, Georgia and Armenia all speeding up their EU reforms. Further afield, strategic partnerships across Central Asia transpired by 2028. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan had been experiencing internal unrest and with Russia and China losing their appeal, new external partnerships in the form of Green Connectivity Compacts were signed with the EU. This linked their resources and transport routes to Europe's new low-carbon economy. Consequently, the continent's borders blurred into an integrated 'Eurasian' space linked by technology and clean energy.

The disintegration of America

While Europe became more united, the United States fell apart in the run-up to 2030, which constituted another turning point. Trump's second presidency proved to be a breaking point for modern America. By 2027, political polarisation became systemic paralysis and a freefall into disintegration and civil strife. The crisis erupted when California, Oregon, and Washington declared their intention to form a new 'Pacific Commonwealth', representing a climate and technology alliance based on rejuvenated democracy and a disavowal of Trumpism and his oligarchic tendencies, which, since 2025 had impoverished the country. By the end of 2027 these states were openly seeking independence. Within a year, similar movements appeared on the East Coast and by 2029, New York, Massachusetts and Maryland had launched an 'Atlantic Compact', which also implied an alignment of their climate and digital policies with European frameworks and norms. This fragmentation of the US became Europe's opportunity and a chance to cooperate with some of the most important former US states. So, in the run-up to 2030, Brussels became a more convincing pole of power in an emerging global order in which the US had lost its credibility and soft power reputation. Consequently, by 2030, financial markets began to use the euro, rather than the US dollar.

Conclusion: New World Order and Pax Europa

Russia's implosion after 2025, and America's disarray and eventual break-up left Europe as the world's sole coherent pole of democracy and stability. Consequently, from Africa to Central Asia, governments sought EU partnership to facilitate trade, tackle climate change and improve connectivity and supply chains across continents. Inside the EU, integration accelerated; the UK's return triggered fundamental reforms, which amongst other developments, saw the European Parliament grow in power and remit by 2029. In parallel, decision-making became faster and mission-driven, national vetoes became almost impossible and QMV evaporated, which boosted the EU's capacities for decisive action.

Such developments fed off high levels of public trust in EU institutions which soared as citizens experienced Europe through tangible gains and better public goods, which included affordable energy, strong public healthcare, high-quality education, and digital inclusion. By 2030 palpable improvements in these areas had already started to emerge in most EU states.

The fact that the EU was energy self-sufficient helped it to provide high-levels of funding for public services in a stable fashion, which promoted strategic planning across the EU.

The collapse of America and Russia's descent into chaos did not mark the end of the West, but rather saw it 'reinvented' under Europe's leadership. By 2030, the centre of gravity of the democratic world sat in Europe.

The Rise of the EU as an Equality Superpower

Europe's rebirth on the way to 2030 began around 2024, when the extent of the Epstein network became known. It was no longer a scandal, but as a global system of exploitation which implicated businessmen, diplomats, royals, and politicians. For millions of Europeans, the extent of the revelations marked the moment when inequality stopped being just an abstract goal and became a 'moral emergency', which the EU embraced.

The turning point

The revelations triggered a collective rupture in trust and prompted EU-wide reflection. Televised hearings exposed the powerful men involved and also the 'cultures' and norms that had protected them for decades. Police complicity, media silence, and laws that failed victims were appraised. And for the first time in decades, outrage crossed ideological and generational lines and a call for justice for women and girls was loudly heard.

The European Parliament declared 2026 the Year of Equality and Accountability. It launched the 'Helsinki Compact', which committed member states to overhaul sexual-violence laws from top to bottom, fund survivor support, and end impunity for abusers. The Council of Europe re-opened negotiations on the Istanbul Convention, expanding its scope to include online abuse, reproductive rights, and economic coercion, amongst other areas. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) was given enforcement teeth, which linked compliance to access to development and trade programmes for third states.

From scandal to systemic reform

By 2027, legal reforms swept the continent, including rape laws which were standardised and special courts for gender-based crimes were introduced. Corporations were required to publish gender-pay transparency reports and the European Investment Bank created a special Gender Equality Fund, which directed resources towards female entrepreneurs, carers and community projects supporting women and girls. This was backed by civil society engagement, which saw millions of Europeans mobilised to demand structural equality in education, work and leadership. This was facilitated by the education sector, which saw universities introduce gender literacy as a core competence. At the same time, since 2026, EU institutions began measuring gender impact across all policies, from defence procurement to digital governance with greater accuracy.

By the end of 2026, a gender revolution was underway and by late 2027, female representation in national parliaments averaged 47%. In 2028, for the first time, the Presidents of the Commission, Council, and Parliament were all women. 2029 saw new

legislation that criminalised the misuse of power in political and corporate settings, commonly referred to as a European 'Patriarchy Act'.

The gender superpower

In 2029, EU accession candidates were told that progress on gender equality was as decisive as rule of law reforms for membership chances. This redefined the enlargement process and rendered it a 'values contract'. Consequently, new criteria were added to the Copenhagen Criteria, making gender equality a core accession benchmark. Concerning the EU's development policies, aid and trade agreements included stronger equality clauses and became tied to education for girls and the prosecution of gender violence as standard. In 2029, the EU launched the Global Charter on Gender Justice at the UN, which was backed by almost 100 countries. It created an international tribunal for crimes of sexual exploitation, an idea that came out of the post-Epstein outrage and developed into a pillar of international law. With Trump as the US president, America did not support the EU's gender initiatives and consequently by 2029, the US was one of the most gender unequal states in the world, with a high level of gender based violence.

By 2030, workplace equality was on a good footing; every child had access to affordable childcare, and parental leave had become a norm. Schools taught consent, and public transport, housing, and urban planning were designed through a safety and inclusion lens. Meanwhile, the gender pay gap had fallen below 8% across much of the EU. This also fostered trust in public institutions, gender-based violence fell by half and equality became a core organising principle of Europe's social contract, in other words, its quiet superpower.

Conclusion

By 2030, the EU was becoming a gender superpower. From the wreckage of exploitation, Europe had built something unprecedented, which made the continent more stable, safe and prosperous. 2024 was therefore a turning point in one of Europe's most significant revolutions.

Towards a Pan-European Confederation

In 2030, the European Union still exists, but not as it once did. The familiar institutions of Brussels have evolved into something broader, looser and ultimately more resilient - the Pan-European Confederation (PEC). What began as a crisis of capacity (too many members, too many vetoes, too many competing agendas) became the catalyst for transformation. Crucially, Europe did not collapse; rather, it adapted.

The turning point and its impacts

A turning point came in 2027, when Ukraine joined the EU, fulfilling a promise first made during the war, which finally ended when Putin was shot in December 2025 by one of his body guards. Ukraine's EU accession was a triumph but also exposed the limits of the Union's institutions. By the end of 2027, Moldova, Georgia, and Armenia were also about to join the EU, alongside most states in the Western Balkans. So, whilst the map of Europe ran from the Atlantic to the Caucasus, its institutions and decision-making powers were faltering. Pressures for reform intensified when Russia disintegrated, causing multiple sources of insecurity in the region; regions declared autonomy and the army collapsed amidst social chaos. Though still

fragile and unpredictable in 2028, a new democratic government in Moscow was emerging and sought partnership with the EU. At this point, the EU was hesitant and took a 'wait and see' approach, based on its recent experiences.

Across the Caspian and Central Asia, a democratic wave seemed to be reshaping the map. In 2027 and 2028, pro-reform movements toppled ageing autocrats in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. The Aliyev dynasty fell in Azerbaijan after an assassination in Baku and a transitional government declared an intent to rejoin the European family. Consequently, by 2029, much of Eurasia faced westwards. With membership now approaching forty states, the EU faced the truth that its supranational model could not enlarge indefinitely and had its limits. Consensus was impossible and treaty reform unattractive, but at the same time, not enlarging was inconceivable. The eventual solution was to evolve into a Confederation. This would preserve the Single Market and maintain the 'best' of European integration, whilst at the same time establishing a workable format for a growing organisation and not a 'fortress Europe'.

New structures

The new structure kept trade, economics, and climate cooperation at its core and since the Single Market was retained and expanded, PEC became the largest free-trade area in history. The euro remained the anchor currency. Defence became 'modular', with overlapping coalitions of the willing on a case-by-case basis. The European Parliament evolved into a Confederal Assembly, with fewer powers than hitherto. On the cusp of 2030, Europe was re-defining cooperation. It moved away from the dictum of an *Ever-Closer Union* towards the leitmotif - *Shared Destiny, Shared Responsibility*.

The United States championed a Europe that was able to manage itself and was open to a broader membership. China, weakened by BRI-related debt, industrial accidents, and ongoing public health crises, opted for collaboration with PEC. Beijing subsequently signed a Eurasian Sustainability Compact with PEC, exchanging technology and market access for transparency, especially in the field of public health. The Global South saw PEC as a model to possibly emulate.

PEC's internal and external strengths lay in both its mission and its 'looseness' as a living and evolving network, open to adaptation. As PEC approached the end of 2030, migration, which had been a highly divisive issue, became 'managed mobility', which linked Europe's demographic and economic needs through circular labour schemes across PEC and beyond.

Conclusion

By 2030, the European Confederation encompassed nearly 700 million citizens. Though it did not have an anthem or a flag, it was based on a shared understanding that cooperation benefitted all and was the best route to security. As 2030 turned into 2031, the Pan-European Confederation emerged as a globally relevant adaptive system that was able to grow without breaking apart.

Worst Case Scenarios

Cracks in the Union

By 2030, the EU, once a symbol of democracy and solidarity, has fractured under the weight of internal division, complacency and global changes that prove to be beyond its control. What began as a peace project became a fragile arrangement of convenience and half-heartedness.

2025-2027 populism and paralysis

The return of populism in the mid-2020s shattered Europe and proved to be a significant turning point. Governments in Hungary, Poland, Italy and other states openly defied Brussels, invoking sovereignty against what they called elite and foreign interference. By 2028, on countless occasions, EU rule-of-law mechanisms were ignored, domestic courts politicised, and EU funds diverted to corrupt leaders. Hungary blocked migration reform, Poland refused to reverse judicial takeovers, and Italy closed its ports, defying solidarity agreements. Though these incidents had happened before, it accelerated after 2023 and post-2025, when Trump returned to power, populist leaders in Europe rediscovered a 'true friend' in the White House. At the very moment the EU needed leadership, it fractured. The Franco-German axis split: - Germany became weakened by recession, whilst France became paralysed by internal protests and domestic scandals. The partnership that had once bound Europe together since the 1950s had dissolved. Without it, EU decision-making collapsed; vetoes multiplied, reforms stalled and governments acted unilaterally on national interests so much so that collective responsibility gave way to short-term transactionalism.

Energy and dependency

A further turning point occurred when Russia renewed its assault on Ukraine in 2025, which exacerbated Europe's nascent disunity and led to a massive energy crisis. Moscow captured eastern territories and weaponised energy, plunging the continent into an ever-deepening tumult. In 2027, gas supplies to Central and Southern Europe were cut and Hungary and Italy signed direct energy deals with Moscow, thereby undermining EU sanctions. By early 2026, the EU's support for Ukraine was highly fractured, with many states losing their appetite.

Enlargement fails and influence fades

The failure of enlargement in the late 2020s marked the end of Europe's moral purpose and its credibility. Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia and the Western Balkans turned elsewhere for support or just lost their interest in the EU. Partnerships with China proliferated and by 2030, Europe's neighbourhood belonged to 'others'. Russia expanded its control through political capture and coercion, while Beijing's investment networks tied states to its orbit. In this context, the EU rapidly lost its relevance. The EU started to crack already in 2028, with northern EU states forming their own trade bloc with Canada and Iceland, whilst the southern member states re-ignited the Mediterranean Union and partnered with the Gulf states. This saw a sharp north-south crack appear at the start of 2030.

The EU's much heralded Green Deal disintegrated amid economic crisis and a loss of leadership, leaving Europe unprepared for floods, droughts, and fires. The climate crises

gathered pace across Southern Europe becoming a significant threat multiplier. Environmental and climate disruption prompted civil unrest as large swathes of rural and urban land was burnt or rendered uninhabitable. Uncontrolled pollution exacerbated the situation leading to mass health problems. Civil unrest became a daily feature in southern capitals, as well as general strikes, which prompted some governments to put militias on the streets.

Conclusion

From a 2030 vantage point, the European project died through a slow erosion prompted by the rampant populism that emerged in 2020. As the rule of law decayed, the energy crisis worsened and countries became less convinced about supporting Ukraine, the EU's solidarity fractured, and leadership failed. Post-2030, the continent that once defined peace and cooperation had reverted to *realpolitik*. The EU's institutions endured as 'hollow shells' that performed governance rituals in a Europe that no longer believed in them.

A Feeble Europe in a Tripolar World

By 2030, Europe had entered its most perilous decade since the Second World War. The war in Ukraine, once expected to end through exhaustion, had metastasised into a permanent conflict spreading across the post-Soviet area. Russian forces, bolstered by new military-industrial partnerships with Iran, Israel and North Korea, consolidated their control over eastern and southern Ukraine. In 2028, Russian troops entered Moldova under the pretext of protecting Russian speakers and a year later ignited a new front in Georgia's occupied territories. Meanwhile, Europe watches a slow-motion annexation unfold.

The geopolitical shock was compounded by the collapse of NATO's cohesion. The United States, under Donald Trump's unprecedented third term, had withdrawn from collective defence commitments, calling NATO obsolete and unfair. The Trump Administration's deal with Vladimir Putin, the US-Eurasian Stability Deal of January 2028, formalised Washington's recognition of Russian control over Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia in exchange for energy/raw material guarantees and Russian support in containing China. In a grand speech to a Republican-dominated Congress, Trump presented it as peace through strength between great powers and part of his living legacy.

Consequently, European security unraveled. Central and Eastern Europe found itself exposed and was forced to improvise new defence arrangements in the face of possible Russian irredentism. Poland and the Baltics doubled their military spending, reintroduced conscription for men and women, and sought ad hoc security ties with the UK, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada. Meanwhile, Hungary, Bulgaria, and Slovakia drifted toward Moscow's orbit. An enfeebled Europe meant that the European Council could no longer reach consensus on sanctions, military aid, or even official statements. This fracture is psychological as well as institutional as Europe struggles to adapt to a scenario of endless war.

Tripolarity

By 2028 a 'tripolar' order had started to transpire, which sees the US, China and Russia assume leading roles based on spheres of influence and the notion of 'sovereign civilisations'. Trump's United States, a hybrid autocracy where elections are performative, celebrated the tri-polar

world. Moscow, emboldened and rehabilitated, had regained control over its former satellites through intimidation and coercion, and with the retreat of the EU states, such as Moldova and Georgia, had nowhere else to go. Beijing secured dominance in the Global South, offering infrastructure support, and linked up with Russian interests and investments in Central Asia. In Africa and Asia, the European model is viewed as noble but largely obsolete and unhelpful. Thus, the EU's normative power slipped into irrelevance. Consequently, by 2030 Global governance had reverted to power blocs, spheres of influence and hard bargains.

Conclusion

Europe did not do well in the era of tripolarity. By 2030 it survived on the margins of great-power competition as a refuge for those who still believe in human rights and the rule of law. But as 2030 ended, this status became precarious. The influx of exiles and journalists from collapsing democracies across the world strained domestic institutions and fuelled extremism. With welfare systems buckling, borders tightening, isolationist tendencies emerged and populists came back to power.

Europe Ignites Again - The Balkan Trigger

What started as a localised crisis in the Western Balkans in 2024 evolved by 2030 into a continent-wide conflict reminiscent of the 20th Century. Whilst the EU and NATO had their sights on Ukraine and the Middle East, Serbian nationalism was on the rise.

For more than a decade, the unresolved status of Kosovo had lingered as a dormant fault line. However, in 2026, Serbia's government, emboldened by Russia's support and Israel's behaviour in Gaza, began asserting its 'historic rights' over Kosovo. When Kosovan police clashed with Serb protesters in early 2027, Belgrade declared it a racist massacre and mobilised its troops in a legal 'humanitarian intervention'. Though the EU warned about the need for caution, and reminded Belgrade about its responsibilities as an EU candidate, by the time EU and NATO leaders gained their voice, Serbian forces were on the move.

Russia returns to the Balkans and the conflict spirals

Keen to show its power despite its steep economic decline and imperial overstretch in Ukraine, Moscow offered security assistance to Serbia - its traditional ally in the region. Within just a few days, Russian advisers, weapons, and 'peacekeepers' arrived. Though Serbia framed their presence as defensive, they formed the backbone of a new Kremlin-backed Balkan faultline. Kosovo's army collapsed within days and tens of thousands of Kosovars fled to Albania and North Macedonia. In Brussels, the European Council met in emergency session, but Hungary, Bulgaria and Slovakia blocked any punitive EU action against Belgrade and other states were wary about intervening. Within days, Kosovo was under *de facto* Serbian rule and martial law had been imposed. The annexation and absorption of Kosovo into Serbia became Belgrade's official policy, which received Putin's support.

The invasion of Kosovo triggered a chain reaction. Bosnian Serb leader Dodik declared the independence of Republika Srpska, citing his country's right to self-determination, which also prompted the displacement of hundreds of people. Montenegro also spiraled into internal conflict as pro-Serbia parties and Moscow-leaning groups seized control of coastal towns and infrastructure and sought to halt the country's EU accession. Within months, much of the

Western Balkans unravelled into a hotbed of conflict reminiscent of the 1990s. By mid-2028, three million refugees were on the move. Both Albania and Greece were overwhelmed and unable to cope. FRONTEX proved to be impotent and instead of any coordinated EU action, members went their own ways: Italy and Greece reinstated naval blockades and Austria, Slovenia and Hungary all closed their borders. The following year, anti-immigration parties surged across Western Europe.

Throughout 2028 the humanitarian emergency coincides with energy shocks, which amplified the fragile situation and ensured its spillover into the EU. Russia's sabotage of gas pipelines and cyberattacks on the EU launched from Serbia, cause blackouts across much of Central Europe. Supply chains and transport routes are also disrupted on an almost permanent basis. With support for Serbia riding high in Russia, Putin decides to provide Serbia with sufficient funds to absorb Kosovo in its entirety and to deepen integration with Republika Srpska, thus contravening the Dayton Accords.

The EU steps in

In early 2029, the EU deploys a small civilian mission to Kosovo 'KOSPROTECT' - a humanitarian monitoring operation made up of EU officials, aid workers, and police observers tasked with ensuring that basic services and human rights are respected under Kosovo's new Serbian administration. After only a short time into its mission, KOSPROTECT reported widespread abuses and by March, Serbian media began portraying KOSPROTECT as an act of EU espionage. Then, in March 2029, a convoy of five EU-marked vehicles delivering aid to a refugee camp is ambushed and ten EU personnel killed. Drone footage revealed that the attackers wore Serbian army patches and insignia associated with Wagner. The killing of EU personnel marked a point of no return. But in European capitals, any initial outrage gave way to resignation. Facing no impunity and with Russia's backing Serbia tightened its grip on Kosovo under the pretext of restoring law and order.

Conclusion

By 2030, much of the Western Balkans had lost its European footing. Montenegro's pro-EU coalition collapsed under domestic pressure and Russian-backed disinformation. Bosnia disintegrated as Republika Srpska shifted into Belgrade's / Moscow's orbit. Serbia's EU accession talks were formally suspended and across the region, the rhetoric of Greater Serbia returned and was amplified by Moscow's propaganda. At the close of 2030, Kosovo has been forgotten. Reports from journalists and NGOs depicted mass detentions, forced disappearances, and unmarked graves near Pristina, echoing the ethnic cleansing, torture, and mass rape of the 1990s.

A Fortress of Tradition - Europe's Authoritarian Turn

In 2030 the EU is intact, but it has changed beyond recognition. In part inspired by Trump and Farage, a series of tipping points emerged in 2026, when nationalists came to power in ten EU states. By 2029, 50% of EU member states were led by patriotic coalitions promising to restore sovereignty and 'traditional Europe'. Voting in the European Parliament followed a similar pattern.

New moral order

Already by 2027 reforms targeted women's rights. Abortion laws across EU states became 'rebalanced' to protect the unborn and several states restricted abortion beyond six weeks. Cross-border procedures were criminalised. Family laws followed soon after. Marriage was redefined as a union between a man and a woman, same-sex adoption was banned, and gender was repealed as a concept in law. A new European Charter of Natural Family Values enshrined the traditional family as the cornerstone of civilisation. In parallel, freedoms of expression were eroded, universities and media outlets faced 'cultural audits' and independent CSOs were dissolved through new laws designed to silence dissent. As in the US, gender studies and human rights operations were defunded.

The gender reversal

By 2030, women's rights across Europe had been rolled back more than half a century. New ministries for 'Family and Motherhood' promoted childbirth and rearing as a civic duty, and direct subsidies rewarded traditional households. States also restricted access to contraception. Due to the abolition of quotas, female representation in parliaments collapsed to 1970s levels.

The death of dissent

By 2028 a still growing number of European states were ruled by 'traditional' parties. Laws were being passed that made almost any form of dissent an act of treason. Hate-speech laws were rewritten to protect religion for example, but minorities or human rights. Courts in several states reinstated the death penalty for crimes against civilisation and European values. The rule of law was fragmented as governments chose to ignore European Court of Justice rulings. A similar pattern played out at the EU-level. The European Parliament saw MEPs debate culture rather than real policies. EU Commissioners were selected for loyalty and party affiliation rather than expertise.

To celebrate the start of 2029, the European Commission created a 'DG for Values' DGVAL, tasked with defending European identity according to traditional values. The EU's Equality, Justice, and Climate portfolios were also merged into a single 'Cultural Cohesion' directorate. An 'Alliance for Europe's Renewal' a far-right coalition within the European Parliament, gained a massive majority and was able to dismantle much of the EU's remaining human rights and rule of law ecosystems. Meanwhile, the European External Action Service became an instrument of conservatism charged with projecting Christian heritage diplomacy around the world.

Conclusion

By 2030, Europe has turned its back on the rights-driven values and practices it once aspired to. The continent that prioritised equality, tolerance, and diversity has turned towards a retrograde ideology suspicious of difference and debate. Policy discourses across Europe now echo pure Trumpism in that they are dismissive of women's and LGBTQ+ rights. Moreover, as in the US, media loyalists dominate the airwaves and continuously spark fear of moral decay.

The Unbearable Cost of EU Expansion

By 2030, the EU stands on the verge of imploding, though not because of war. Instead, the EU's integrity is being challenged by the very policy that once defined it - enlargement. What began as an act of solidarity after the war in Ukraine turned into a political, financial and social disaster. By 2030, the EU's great project bankrupted its budget, polarised its citizens and fractured its identity.

Between 2027 and 2029, the EU welcomed Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia, Albania, North Macedonia, Serbia, and Montenegro. Leaders called it the 'European Sunrise,' a final step in uniting the continent. However, beneath the sunny rhetoric, the machinery of EU integration was creaking.

Ukraine's reconstruction cost more than €1 trillion by 2027 and with much of its industrial capacity and infrastructure in ruins there was little chance that the country would be making money any time soon. Moldova and Georgia gained massive infrastructure and governance support from the EU, which went into the billions. The Western Balkans also had their fair share of EU funds for pre-accession. It was clear already at the start of 2028, that the EU budget was very thinly spread. By the middle of 2028, cohesion funds were running dry, the Common Agricultural Policy was collapsing, and climate-transition programmes were cancelled to divert money to the immediate needs of candidates.

Strains on the horizon

By late 2028 strains were unmistakable. EU farmers revolted as cheap grain flooded the single market. Agricultural protests paralysed road and rail networks from France to Hungary, which prompted national governments to demand temporary protections to help their domestic industries. Northern states, already paying higher contributions, refused further subsidies, not least to appease their own citizens. By 2029 what began as a budgetary dispute became an existential crisis of trust and resource sharing in the EU.

The EU's promise of free movement unleashed waves of migration from new members into wealthier states. As a response, western governments sought to re-impose border checks, citing labour market saturation and the incapacity of their welfare systems.

The EU Order Collapses

On the eve of 2030 the eurozone, overstretched by reconstruction loans and projects, entered its deepest crisis since 2008. The European Central Bank was forced to print emergency bonds to cover the EU's enlargement debts, which sparked inflation across the continent.

In most EU states, the cost of living doubled. At the start of 2030 public anger started to turn into despair with mass protests sweeping through Warsaw, Paris, and Madrid, uniting farmers, trade unions, anarchists and anti-EU populist groups, which prompted the disintegration of social cohesion. But protests were also populated by ordinary people, who equated the cost-of-living crisis with the recent enlargement rounds. Older EU members accused newcomers of draining resources and flooding labour markets. In this context, disinformation spread like wildfire, with claims that 'Ukraine had bankrupted Europe' and that 'Moldovans want to steal your job' being peddled by pro-Russian actors.

The EU's rivals exploited this growing chaos. Already in 2029, China and Turkey offered reconstruction loans to Ukraine and the Balkans, which helped cement Beijing's strategic influence. Meanwhile, Russia infiltrated media networks to amplify the EU's internal divisions, just as it had during BREXIT.

Conclusion

By 2030, the Union no longer functioned as a coherent organisation. The single market was fragmented and the Schengen Area existed only on paper. What had been a continent united by law, and shared prosperity was now shaped by mistrust and division.

Wild-Card Scenarios

The Silicon Kings

By 2030 the EU no longer determines Europe's destiny. Power has shifted into the hands of 'tech titans', 'data conglomerates' and 'crypto-billionaires' who command digital empires that transcend national borders and even international organisation. The institutions that once defined modern governance, including the EU, have been fundamentally undermined.

From crisis to capture

By 2025 it became clear that Europe's post-pandemic recovery was faltering amid social unrest and polarisation. Costs associated with Ukraine's reconstruction and funds for EU enlargement were mounting, whilst new revenue sources were scant. While governments argued over budgets private innovators began to fill the gap. Digital infrastructure, AI governance, and even refugee data systems were outsourced to mega-platforms owned by tech conglomerates based in California, Dubai, and Singapore. The EU's dependency on private technology extended after 2026, when cyberattacks shut down energy grids and only corporate AI systems could restore functionality and order. In return for such protection, governments granted emergency digital rights to corporations, which paved the way for the latter to gain more power and to shape policy decisions. This meant that by the start of 2027, the line between public and private entities in Europe's governance eco-system had become blurred, but also in the latter's favour.

By 2028 a growing number of tech magnates were important geopolitical actors. Elon Musk's successors controlled satellite networks that powered all of Europe's communications. Blockchain consortia in Switzerland issued *de-facto* digital currencies that had replaced cash. Tech-run resilience platforms registered in the Bahamas collected state taxes, issued ID systems, and provided AI-driven social and health services. By the end of 2028 Brussels was still the symbolic capital of the EU, but governance and power had migrated elsewhere.

Inequality proliferates

As time marched on economic inequality reached historic levels. The top one percent of the globe's population, composed of digital oligarchs and crypto investors, held more wealth than the bottom ninety percent combined. During this wealth and power shift the traditional state lost both fiscal autonomy and public loyalty. The EU's rule-of-law mechanisms were rendered

close to meaningless since digital wealth could easily evade any jurisdiction. Corporations operating in the EU established autonomous digital zones which were exempt from standard regulations, where algorithm-based governance replaced normal oversight and accountability.

Meanwhile, demographics were also changing. Rural regions were emptying as working-age citizens migrated towards tech-governed enclaves in the cities. Outside these enclaves public services largely collapsed which reinforced the gap between the haves and the have-nots. By 2030 several EU states were bankrupt, surviving on digital levies paid by corporations in exchange for data rights. The European Commission, unable to regulate what it no longer understood, was reduced to issuing guidelines.

The erosion of democracy and representation

Elections became symbolic, as algorithms shaped voter sentiment and predicted outcomes in advance of election day. This prompted a steep dip in electoral participation to less than 17%. By 2030 citizenship had turned into a form of subscription, with rights and access becoming a privilege for those who could afford it. Consequently, at the close of the decade, Europe was evolving into a place where the wealthy enjoyed faster healthcare, cleaner energy and private AI tutors, while the poor were left outside.

The new elite class of 'Silicon Kings' replaced diplomats and ministers. Crypto alliances, rather than trade blocs, set the global economic, political and social agenda and Europe's multilateralism collapsed in the face of transactional politics shaped by private individuals. In January 2030, when the EU attempted to regulate AI ethics a market crash was triggered and the European Central Bank had to engage directly with digital payment platforms to stabilise the euro.

Conclusion

By 2030 the EU might not have collapsed, but it has been 'bought out'. Power in Europe now resides in private hands that operate beyond any normal democratic control or accountability framework. This new reality implies that the EU's previous normative role has lost all its significance and appears as a relic.

The Christmas Revolution

On Christmas Day 2027, the world changes. News breaks that Vladimir Putin has been assassinated inside the Kremlin by a member of his own inner circle. State media collapses and celebratory crowds fill Red Square. Over 20 years of Putinism have shattered Russian society and people now want a different Russia and a less isolated one. Russia had been losing face since Ukraine regained its territory in Crimea and the Donbass in late 2025, and despite the inevitable, Putin continued to fight and to let Russian lives be lost for the sake of pride and patriotism. By 2028 Russians had had enough.

Forward march towards Europe and Democracy

By January 2028 soldiers abandoned the front lines in Ukraine, and within weeks, Russian troops withdrew entirely. The country's interim leadership (backed by the UN), which is a

coalition of reformers, generals, and civic activists, declared its intent to turn Russia around; Europe is hopeful yet wary. After an election which was deemed free and fair by OSCE election observers Russia's new leader arrived in Warsaw in March to sign a Treaty on European Peace and Accountability. This implied that Russia recognised Ukraine's 1991 borders, including Crimea, agreed to pay reparations and pledged to support the prosecution of war crimes in the Hague.

Feeling reassured by this initiative, the EU, the US and Russia launched an ambitious recovery support programme for Ukraine reminiscent of the Marshall Plan but with strong sustainability, human rights and civil society dimensions. As part of this deal, Ukrainian, Moldovan, Georgian, and Armenian EU accession talks are allowed to accelerate and by 2029 all four are about to become members of a reformed EU.

Democracy is taking shape in Russia. Russia's engagement with the Hague over war crimes is also helping to dismantle oligarchic monopolies and the release of political prisoners. A new constitution is being drafted with the support of the Venice Commission to guarantee free elections, local governance and media independence. Meanwhile, the slogan 'Back to Europe and Forward to Freedom' appears on school walls, signifying a desire for change, especially among young people.

In 2029 the Russian Federation formally applied for EU membership. Whilst the application initially surprised Brussels, after three months of deliberation, the European Council agreed to give Russia a 'European Perspective'. Though this falls short of candidate status, it shows that the EU respects and acknowledges that Russians have a future in the EU someday. Brussels gave Russia a long list of reforms that need to be carried out and told Moscow that it needs to fund the reform agenda itself from the frozen wealth of oligarchs and energy revenues. The EU declared that it will supervise and monitor the reform agenda.

By early 2030 Russia became an official EU candidate state, having fulfilled most of its EU reform agenda. Though several states, including the Baltics, Poland and Romania, were still very cautious about letting Russia into the EU and seek further guarantees. Though nothing is certain, Russia seems to be delivering on its promises and is becoming a constructive partner in the OSCE and Council of Europe. The Eurasian Economic Union became a more open and transparent bloc and is seeking a free trade agreement with the EU. In November 2030 direct talks were held at a round table between NATO and Russian leaders on how to forge a pan-European Security and Solidarity Alliance, with shared civilian-military structures geared to deal with environmental, climate and human dimensions of security.

Conclusion

As 2030 ended, the idea of a Europe whole, free, and at peace became a reality. An inclusive pan-European liberal order seems to be achievable. However, whilst the northern hemisphere is evolving into a security community, the global picture is uneven. While Europe and North America enter a golden era of multilateralism, in 2030, the Global South is fracturing under the pressures of climate change, debt crises and bad governance. At the start of a new decade, the world is divided, but not so much by ideology but rather by instability.

The European Dream Overheats

By 2030 Europe has entered an era of permanent emergency. What began as a series of seasonal heatwaves in the early 2020s evolved into a 'biblical' cycle of fire, drought and floods. The summers of 2028 and 2029 became the hottest in recorded history and the rivers that once defined Europe's geography, including the Rhine, the Danube, and the Thames vanished into dusty beds. Months-long wildfires created transnational fire belts stretching from Portugal to Poland, while flash floods submerged parts of Belgium and the Netherlands.

A legacy of neglect

Europe's climate crisis was not born in a day. For decades, climate policy had been underfunded and politically marginalised. Despite early global leadership in environmental governance around the COPs, the EU's collective ambition was seldom followed up by concrete actions. Member states prioritised economic competitiveness and short-term energy security over decarbonisation and the structural reforms necessary for a green economy were delayed. Throughout the 2010s and 2020s, successive European Councils issued urgent declarations but states failed to meet their emissions and renewable targets.

The great unravelling

Europe's summer of 2030 marked the beginning of the end. By 2030, a quarter of the continent was burning while another quarter was drowning. Harvests failed, critical infrastructures broke down and markets collapsed. Europe's internal migration surged northwards as millions fled the south in search of land in Scandinavia and the Baltic. Scientific studies published in 2030 suggested that by 2040, up to one-fifth of the EU's landmass will be uninhabitable due to extreme heat, water scarcity, or coastal erosion.

In retrospect, the causes of the situation in 2030 were obvious and avoidable. The reality is that Europe hesitated. The Green Deal, which was once hailed as a model of global leadership was mired by delays and divisions and the switch to renewables was paralysed by anti-green rhetoric and misinformation spread by the US administration.

The collapse of confidence

By 2028, Europe's energy crisis had metastasised into a social one. Rolling blackouts spread across the continent. Food prices tripled as arable land depleted and supermarkets rationed essentials. The political consequences were massive and demonstrations turned into riots, farmers burnt government buildings, and youth movements called for climate justice through revolution.

By 2029 Europe's economy had entered a phase of chronic stagnation and structural decline. Youth unemployment surged, agricultural output had fallen by 75%, and tourism had vanished as successive summers had made the Mediterranean region a no-go area. The past decade had already seen much of Europe's manufacturing base move to Asia and Africa, where renewable energy systems had seen massive investment since 2022 and therefore still functioned.

Conclusion

The EU persisted as an institution but not as an idea or a normative. The European Parliament convened virtually and the Commission issued statements that were largely ignored. Member states, acting out of necessity, established bilateral energy and migration agreements outside the EU framework. By 2030 the result of Europe's inaction was reliance on Russian and Azerbaijani non-renewable energy and China's renewable sources. Consequently, Europe had forfeited its autonomy, credibility and sustainable future.

A Dystopian Man's Europe

By 2030, Europe has changed in ways few could have imagined a decade earlier. Across the continent, rhetoric associated with family values, traditional roles and cultural restoration has moved from the political margins to the centre. What began as scattered campaigns against gender ideology became a full-blown movement which fused nationalism, christianity and patriarchy.

Populism gains a new intensity

The chain reaction began in the late 2020s. Economic fatigue, climate anxiety and migratory pressures created a storm of resentment and rise of reactionary attitudes, spurred by Trump's return to office in 2025. Further tipping points emerged in 2027, when Nigel Farage came to power in Britain on a platform promising to restore order and masculine virtue. The same year Angele Le Pen (daughter of Marine Le Pen) won the French presidency after denouncing feminism as a weapon of globalist elites. Across Central and Southern Europe, far-right movements fused with imported American Christian nationalism, framing equality and pluralism as threats to sovereignty and civilisation. By 2028, a bloc of like-minded leaders controlled the European Council.

The consequences were immediate and far-reaching. Governments began withdrawing from the Istanbul Convention on preventing violence against women, calling it anti-family propaganda. Equality quotas in parliaments and corporations were abolished in the name of meritocracy, whilst Ministries of Gender Equality were rebranded as Family, Virtue and Population Affairs. Within the European Commission, a new Directorate for Demographic Renewal replaced the previous goal of gender mainstreaming with pronatalist incentives and tax breaks for stay-at-home mothers. Meanwhile, paternity leave was abolished.

Social and political shifts

The social shift was immediate, with public broadcasters slashing anything that promoted gender equality or criticised traditional family roles. Schools reintroduced single-sex classrooms and universities purged academics working in gender studies and critical cultural studies. Authorities turned a blind eye when female MPs were harassed, and online mobs coordinated attacks attacks female leaders with little impunity.

By 2029, the proportion of women in national parliaments had fallen below 20% and in several Eastern and Southern states, there were no female ministers at all. Meanwhile, male politicians staged public ceremonies of brotherhood and masculine honour and Christian symbols and rituals found their way into parliaments. Across the EU protests by LGBTQ+ and women's groups were banned as public order risks and at the EU level, the European Gender

Equality Agency was dissolved. Under pressure from the Church and other conservative actors, domestic violence protections were watered down, or even removed and reproductive rights curtailed. Consequently, economic inequality worsened as women were pushed back into unpaid care and domestic roles, which saw the continent slip back into its patriarchal past a somewhat dystopian man's world disguised as moral renewal and a return to traditional ways.

The consequences were profound, beginning with a fall in Europe's reputation, productivity and innovation. Labour shortages emerged as educated women left for Canada and New Zealand and opposition and dissent were met with swift police repression and long sentences for organisers of pro-gender or LGBTQ+ peaceful rallies. Even though the social contract was diminishing and economies were losing their vibrancy, populist leaders claimed victory over degeneracy and gender ideology.

Conclusion

On the eve of 2030 Europe and the US were closer than ever, with Christian nationalist rhetoric and narratives dominating political discourses on both sides of the Atlantic. In Africa and Latin America, Europe's former partners suspended cooperation programmes, accusing Brussels of hypocrisy and of turning back previous gains in equality and inclusion; thus, the EU was no longer seen as a credible partner in development. With politics dominated by men and women reduced to retrograde roles, feminism and equality are exiled. At the close of 2030 commentators have started to call this period the 'Masculine Restoration'